

Supplemental Information for:

Multidimensional plasticity of phenology: Assessing the effects of population density on plastic responses of breeding time to temperature

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Appendix 1: Data distributions and structure

We investigated the reason behind clustering of the data in the plots we made with the temperature data, and the plot below shows temperature readings from the sliding widow for each year of study. The histogram shows certain years having temperature readings being very similar causing the cluster pattern (Fig S1).

Figure S1: Distribution of the 23 years (1994-2016) with respective spring temperature values.

Figure S2: Variation in territory sizes from 1994-2016, per patch. Red dots represent mean overall territory (all patches combined) size for a given year in meters square.

Figure S3: Variation in patch level densities from 1994-2016, per patch measured as the number of occupied nest boxes (NB) per hectare. Mean overall global densities per site are provided in the table below

Table S3: Variation in patch level densities. Overall patch density was calculated as the total number of available nestboxes per hectare for each patch. Mean patch density was calculated as the mean number of occupied nestboxes per hectare over 23 years.

Patches →	HN	KB	LO	ZZ
Total available nest boxes	23.00	90.00	62.00	96.00
Total area of patch (Hectare)	2.80	10.10	6.20	11.10
Overall patch density	8.21	8.91	10.00	8.65
Mean patch density (all years)	3.87	4.13	4.25	3.47

Figure S4: Correlation between patch level density (number of occupied nestboxes/ha) and territory level density (territory sizes in m²). The estimated correlation between territory and patch level density measures is of -0.35 (95% CI [-0.39, -0.31]) indicating that 12.25% of the variance in territory sizes is explained by the variance in patch density.

Appendix 2: Results

Part 1: Effects of distance to the nearest neighbour (nearest occupied nest box) on laying date and fledging success in great tits

We considered the distance to the nearest occupied nest box as our second proxy to investigate the effects of density at territory level. Note that the distance to the nearest nest box is in meters, and was considered as the nearest great tit inhabiting the nest box.

Figure S5: Effect of temperature and territory level density using distance to nearest neighbour as proxy for density at local scale on egg-laying date in great tits. Dots represent individual (raw) data points of laying date according to mean spring temperature with jitter to reduce overlap. Regression lines represent predictions from model including interaction of density proxy and temperature, the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for territory level density proxy. Note that large distances correspond to low local density.

Table S5 A & B: Effect of temperature and territory level density using distance to nearest neighbour as proxy for density at local scale on egg-laying date in great tits (LMM, $N_{\text{Obs}}=2166$, $N_{\text{females}}=1231$,

$N_{\text{Years}}=23$; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on neighbour distance as territory level density proxy. B) Analysis splitting nearest neighbour distance into among and within individual components.

A	Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
	(Intercept)	103.42	0.54	36207.32	< 0.0001
	Spring temperature	-5.13	0.32	261.92	< 0.0001
	Female age (Older)	-1.88	0.18	106.49	< 0.0001
	Nearest neighbour distance	-0.55	0.10	31.56	< 0.0001
	Nearest neighbour distance x temperature	0.02	0.09	0.07	0.80

B	Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
	(Intercept)	103.42	0.54	36295.80	< 0.0001
	Spring temperature	-5.13	0.32	261.93	< 0.0001
	Female age (Older)	-1.88	0.18	105.65	< 0.0001
	Among-individual	-0.45	0.13	12.59	< 0.0001
	Within-individual	-0.33	0.07	19.49	< 0.0001
	Among-individual x temperature	-0.03	0.09	0.08	0.77
	Within-individual x temperature	0.08	0.09	0.68	0.41

Table S6 A & B: Effects of territory level density using distance to nearest neighbour as proxy for density at local scale and egg-laying date on fledging success in great tits ($N_{\text{Obs}}=2165$, years =23; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on distance to nearest neighbour as territory level density proxy. B) Analysis splitting distance to nearest neighbour into among and within individual components.

A				
Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	3.27	0.23	14.15	< 0.0001
Neighbour distance	0.02	0.01	2.65	< 0.001

Laying date	-0.01	0.00	-5.69	< 0.0001
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.14	0.26
Spring temperature	-0.03	0.01	-2.47	0.01
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	-6.77	2.13	-3.18	< 0.001
Nearest neighbour distance	0.00	0.01	-0.48	0.63
Laying date	0.04	0.02	2.39	0.01
Female age (Older)	0.45	0.17	2.66	< 0.001
Spring temperature	0.04	0.09	0.38	0.70

B

Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	2.08	0.02	100.57	< 0.0001
Spring temperature	-0.04	0.02	-2.47	0.01
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.19	0.23
Laying date	-0.07	0.01	-5.61	< 0.0001
Among-individual	0.03	0.01	3.49	< 0.001
Within-individual	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	-2.80	0.15	-18.45	< 0.0001
Spring temperature	0.05	0.14	0.39	0.70
Female age (Older)	0.45	0.17	2.65	< 0.001
Laying date	0.27	0.11	2.39	0.02
Among-individual	-0.06	0.09	-0.70	0.48
Within-individual	0.01	0.08	0.11	0.91

Figure S6: Effect of temperature and territory level density using distance to nearest neighbour as proxy for density at local scale on fledging success in great tits. Regression lines represent predictions from hurdle model with the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for territory size. (A) Effect of spring temperature and distance to nearest neighbour on the number of fledged young. (B) Effect of laying date and distance to nearest neighbour on number of fledged young. (C) Effect of laying date and distance to nearest neighbour on the likelihood of failure. Note that in figures A, B and C raw data points have been superimposed over model predictions. In figure C the raw data are in binomial format.

Part 2: Effects of density on laying dates (blue tits and great tits combined)

Table S7 A & B: Effects of territory level density and temperature using territory size as a proxy for density at local scale on egg-laying date in great tits (LMM, $N_{\text{Obs}}=2180$, $N_{\text{females}}=1234$, $N_{\text{Years}}=23$; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on territory size as territory level density proxy. B) Analysis splitting territory size into among and within individual components.

A	Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
	(Intercept)	103.38	0.47	48934.92	< 0.0001
	Spring temperature	-5.14	0.32	257.50	< 0.0001
	Female age (Older)	-1.96	0.18	114.25	< 0.0001
	Territory size	-0.35	0.10	12.11	< 0.0001
	Territory size x temperature	-0.02	0.09	0.03	0.86

B	Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
	(Intercept)	103.39	0.47	47623.73	< 0.0001
	Spring temperature	-5.14	0.32	258.94	< 0.0001
	Female age (Older)	-1.96	0.18	113.99	< 0.0001
	Among-individual	-0.21	0.12	2.91	0.09
	Within-individual	-0.24	0.08	10.06	<0.001
	Among-individual x temperature	-0.03	0.09	0.10	0.75
	Within-individual x temperature	0.01	0.09	0.02	0.90

Table S8 A & B: Effects of patch level density and temperature in great tits (LMM, $N_{\text{Obs}}=2180$, $N_{\text{females}}=1234$, $N_{\text{Years}}=23$; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on density at patch level. B) Analysis splitting patch level density into among and within individual components.

A	Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
	(Intercept)	103.41	0.49	44832.44	< 0.0001
	Spring temperature	-5.16	0.32	258.41	< 0.0001
	Female age (Older)	-1.95	0.18	112.77	< 0.0001
	Patch density	0.09	0.18	0.28	0.60
	Patch density x temperature	-0.09	0.11	0.71	0.40

B

Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	103.41	0.49	44347.72	< 0.0001
Spring temperature	-5.18	0.32	265.81	< 0.0001
Female age (Older)	-1.94	0.18	111.64	< 0.0001
Among-individual	-0.07	0.19	0.15	0.70
Within-individual	0.12	0.10	1.27	0.26
Among-individual x temperature	-0.06	0.10	0.30	0.59
Within-individual x temperature	-0.10	0.10	1.01	0.31

Part 3: Effects of density and laying dates on breeding success (blue tits and great tits combined)

Table S5 A & B: Effects of territory level density using territory size as proxy for density at local scale and temperature on fledging success in great tits ($N_{\text{Obs}}=2175$, years =23; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on territory size as territory level density proxy. B) Analysis splitting territory size into among and within individual components

Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	2.08	0.03	82.66	< 0.0001
Territory size	0.01	0.01	1.07	0.28
Egg-laying date	-0.07	0.01	-5.88	< 0.0001
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.23	0.22
Spring temperature	-0.04	0.02	-2.53	0.01
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-2.81	0.16	-17.51	< 0.0001
Territory size	0.03	0.08	0.32	0.75
Egg-laying date	0.28	0.11	2.45	0.01
Female age (Older)	0.45	0.17	2.66	0.01
Spring temperature	0.06	0.14	0.41	0.68

Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	2.08	0.03	81.74	< 0.0001
Among-individual	0.01	0.01	1.32	0.19
Within-individual	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.98
Egg-laying date	-0.07	0.01	-5.89	< 0.0001
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.23	0.22
Spring temperature	-0.04	0.02	-2.55	0.01
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-2.81	-0.16	17.50	< 0.0001
Among-individual	0.02	0.09	0.26	0.80
Within-individual	0.01	0.08	0.20	0.85

Egg-layingdate	0.28	0.11	2.45	0.01
Female age (Older)	0.45	0.17	2.66	0.01
Spring temperature	0.06	0.14	0.41	0.68

Table S6 A & B: Effects of patch density and egg-laying date on fledging success in great tits ($N_{\text{Obs}}=2175$, years =23; for age, the reference level is one-year old females). A) Analysis based on patch density. B) Analysis splitting patch density into among and within individual components.

Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	2.08	0.03	82.87	< 0.0001
Patch density	-0.02	0.01	-1.41	0.16
Laying date	-0.07	0.01	-5.94	< 0.0001
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.17	0.24
Spring temperature	-0.04	0.02	-2.51	0.01
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	-2.81	0.15	-18.56	< 0.0001
Patch density	0.14	0.09	1.55	0.12
Laying date	0.27	0.11	2.39	0.02
Female age (Older)	0.46	0.17	2.72	0.01
Spring temperature	0.04	0.14	0.33	0.74

Number of Fledglings				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	2.08	0.03	83.26	< 0.0001
Spring temperature	-0.04	0.02	-2.49	0.01
Female age (Older)	0.02	0.02	1.17	0.24
Laying date	-0.07	0.01	-5.93	< 0.0001
Among-individual	-0.01	0.01	-1.08	0.28
Within-individual	-0.01	0.01	-1.19	0.24
Likelihood of failure				
Parameters	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	-2.84	0.15	-18.43	< 0.0001
Spring temperature	0.08	0.14	0.55	0.58
Female age (Older)	0.47	0.17	2.75	0.01

Laying date	0.29	0.11	2.50	0.01
Among-individual	0.23	0.09	2.54	0.01
Within-individual	-0.10	0.08	-1.19	0.23

Figure S7: Effect of temperature and density on egg-laying dates of great tits. Dots represent individual (raw) data points of laying date according to mean spring temperature with jitter to reduce overlap. Regression lines represent predictions from model including interaction of density proxy and temperature,

the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for each density proxy. A- Effects of territory level density using territory size as density proxy. B- Effects of global density (number of occupied nest boxes per hectare in each patch). Note that large territory sizes correspond to low territory level density.

Figure S8: Effect of territory level density, laying date and spring temperature on fledging success in great tits. Regression lines represent predictions from hurdle model with the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for territory size. (A) Effect of spring temperature and territory size on the number of fledged young. (B) Effect of laying date and territory size on number of fledged young. (C) Effect of laying date and territory size on the probability of failure. Note that in figures A, B and C raw data points have been superimposed over model predictions. In figure C the raw data are in binomial format.

Figure S9: Effect of patch density, laying date and spring temperature on fledging success in great tits. Regression lines represent predictions from hurdle model with the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for patch density. (A) Effect of spring temperature and patch density on the number of fledged young. (B) Effect of laying date and patch density on number of fledged young. (C) Effect of laying date and patch density on the probability of failure. Note that in figures A, B and C raw data points have been superimposed over model predictions. In figure C the raw data are in binomial format.

GAM Results

In order to explore potential non-linear relationship of laying dates responses to temperature and density, we fit separate GAM models for patch and territory level density. These models included both smoothed additive main effects of temperature and density proxy, and the smoothed interactive effect of temperature and density proxy using thin plate regression spline for the interactive terms. Female identity, year, and study plot were included as random intercepts, and this was common for the separate models exploring territory and patch level density effects on laying dates. We utilised the “mgcv package” in Rstudio to fit the GAM models (Wood 2011).

Part 4: Effect of patch level density on laying dates

Figure S10: Smoothed effects of patch density and spring temperature on laying dates in great tits. Model predictions (regression line in red) from GAM model with the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for patch density. (A) Effect of spring temperature on laying dates. (B) Effect of patch density on laying dates (C) Interactive smoothed effect of spring temperature and patch density on laying dates (basis: thin plate regression spline). Note that in figures A and B raw data points have been superimposed over model predictions. In figure C the gradient represents the predicted laying dates in response scale.

Part 5: Effect of territory level density on laying dates

Figure S11: Smoothed effects of territory level density and spring temperature on laying dates in great tits. Model predictions (regression line in red) from GAM model with the high (0.95) and low (0.05) quantiles for patch density. (A) Effect of spring temperature on laying dates. (B) Effect of territory size on laying dates (C) Interactive smoothed effect of spring temperature and territory size on laying dates (basis: thin plate regression spline). Note that in figures A and B raw data points have been superimposed over model predictions. In figure C the gradient represents the predicted laying dates in response scale.

Tessellation code

Code used for tessellation in provided below (with annotated text indicated after hashtags)

```
# loading required packages -----
library(sf)
library(readxl)
library(tidyverse)
library(lubridate)
library(mapview)

# Loading data file -----

# breeding data
data_gt <- read_excel("file name.xlsx")%>%
  # format date
  mutate(lay_date = lubridate::ymd(LD),
         jday = yday(lay_date))%>%
  # only first broods
  filter(TY == 1)

# tessellation per plot -----

data_complete <- data.frame() #making empty data frame

for(an in sort(unique(data_gt$year))){ # looping for all years

  print(an)

  dta_y <- data_gt%>%
    filter(year == an)

  for(site in unique(dta_y$Geblied)){

    if(site %in% dta_y$Geblied){ # in case there's no data for a given year in a patch

      dta_sy <- dta_y%>%
        mutate(gbpl_Geblied = paste(gbpl,Geblied, sep = "_"))%>%
        filter(Geblied == site )

      st_read("frag_regions_areas_con2019_ZNTF.shp", quiet = T) %>% # loading shape file of plots
        filter(NAME %in% site)%>% # select fields
        rename(Geblied = NAME)%>% # names of patches
        st_union()%>%
        st_transform(crs = 31370) -> AllArea
```

```

# draw tessellation areas
st_as_sf(dta_sy[c("coorx", "coory", "gbpl", "year", "gbpl_Geblied")],
  coords = c("coorx", "coory"), crs = 31370,
  agr = "constant")%>%
  st_union()%>%
  # voronoi tessellation
  st_voronoi()%>%
  st_collection_extract(type = "POLYGON")%>%
  # limit extent to the study site borders
  st_intersection(AllArea)%>%
  # --> sf format
  st_as_sf() -> a

# calculate areas of polygons
a$area <- st_area(a)

# nestboxes locations
st_as_sf(dta_sy[c("coorx", "coory", "gbpl", "year", "gbpl_Geblied")],
  coords = c("coorx", "coory"), crs = 31370,
  agr = "constant") -> b

# identify one polygon per nestbox
data <- b%>%st_join(a)

data_complete <- rbind(data_complete, data)

}
}
}

# function to identify plots
site_year_plot <- function(Geblied_,year_){

  data <- data_gt%>%

  filter(Geblied == Geblied_,
    year == year_)%>%
  mutate(gbpl_Geblied = paste(gbpl,Geblied, sep = "_"))

st_read("frag_regions_areas_con2019_ZNTF.shp", quiet = T) %>% # shape file of plots
# dplyr::select(-c("ID", "AREA", "PERIMETER", "HECTARES")) %>%
filter(NAME == Geblied_)%>%# select fields
rename(Geblied = NAME)%>%

```

```

st_union()%>%
st_transform(crs = 31370) -> AllArea

vor <- st_as_sf(data[c("coorx", "coory", "gbpl", "year")], # Convert gegis to spatial file
               coords = c("coorx", "coory"), crs = 31370,
               agr = "constant")%>%
st_union()%>%
# voronoi tessellation
st_voronoi()%>%
# st_area()
st_collection_extract(type = "POLYGON")%>%

# limit extent
st_intersection(AllArea)%>%
st_as_sf()

vor$area <- st_area(vor)

#loc nichoirs
st_as_sf(data[c("coorx", "coory", "gbpl", "year",'gbpl_Geblied')],
         coords = c("coorx", "coory"), crs = 31370,
         agr = "constant") -> b

data <- b%>%st_join(vor)%>%
mutate(area2 = as.numeric(area))

return(mapview(list(vor,data)))

}

# -----

# merge data (laying date x tessellation)
data_gt2 <- data_gt%>%
mutate(gbpl_Geblied = paste(gbpl,Geblied, sep = "_"))%>%
left_join(data_complete)%>%
mutate(area2 = as.numeric(area))

# use plot function to mention given site and year to generate respective plot
site_year_plot("KB",2011)

```

References

Wood, S. N. 2011. Fast Stable Restricted Maximum Likelihood and Marginal Likelihood Estimation of Semiparametric Generalized Linear Models. - Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology 73: 3–36.